

Mechanical Properties of SiC Fiber Reinforced Al Composites

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ABSTRACT

Multifilament SiC fibers (Nicalon) produced from polycarbosilane by the conversion of organometallic polymer into inorganic have high tensile strength, high heat-resisting and very flexibility. They are yarns consisting of 500 continuous filaments of diameter $13\mu\text{m}$ and length above 300m. And then it enables to fabricate several kinds of woven fabrics. The compatibility between SiC fibers and Al is sufficient and is well suited for the reinforcement of aluminum.

SiC fiber reinforced Al composites, SiC/1100(35v/o), SiC/5052(40v/o) and SiC/6061(25v/o) have been produced by the technique based on the liquid metal pressing method. The tensile strengths of their composites as fabricated were 861, 781 and 690 MPa at room temperature, respectively. The mechanical behavior among these kinds of composites (as fabricated and heat-treated) is discussed in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

Graphite fiber, SiC fiber and aluminum oxide fiber have been synthesized in recent years. Aluminum composites reinforced with these fibers have been studied by Pfeifer et al. (1), Lachman (2), Champion et al. (3) and Webster (4). We also have studied aluminum composite reinforced with SiC fiber (Nicalon) (5). Two kinds of long continuous SiC fibers are now manufactured. One is a SiC monofilament (100-140 μm in diameter) made by CVD method with carbon filament as the core. This SiC monofilament is now being produced by the AVCO Systems Division, Lowell, Mass., USA. The other is a coreless, continuous SiC multifilament (13 μm in diameter) made by heat-treating melt-spun polycarbosilane fiber (6). This SiC multifilament is now being produced in pilot plant quantities as Nicalon by Nippon Carbon Co., Ltd. (NCK) Japan. This Nicalon is very fine and flexible. In making metal composites of complex shape, this Nicalon is considered to be superior to the SiC monofilament.

Kasai et al. (7) report that this Nicalon is easily compatible with metals and is promising for the reinforcement of metal composites. We prepared aluminum composite reinforced with Nicalon (SiC/Al) by the liquid metal pressing method. We report that the tensile strengths of SiC/6061 and SiC/1100 obey the rule of mixtures up to a fiber volume fraction of $\sim 40\%$, and the strengths are not

influenced by temperature up to 400°C, but are decreased at 500°C (8).

In this work, Nicalon reinforced 1100, 5052 and 6061 aluminum composites have been prepared by the liquid metal pressing method. The mechanical behaviors of these composites (as fabricated and heat-treated) have been discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

As the aluminum matrix, 1100, 5052 and 6061 were used. They were sheets of length 120 mm, width 70 mm and thickness 0.3 mm. As the reinforcement SiC fiber, Nicalon was used. It was 300 m long yarns composed of 500 filaments and 13µm in diameter and its tensile strength, tensile modulus, elongation and density were 2550 MPa, 196 GPa, 1.3 % and 2.55 g/cm³, respectively. The aluminum composite reinforced unidirectionally with SiC fibers was prepared by the liquid metal pressing method, as shown in Fig.1 (8).

Three kinds of aluminum composites obtained are SiC/1100 (35 v/o), SiC/5052 (40 v/o) and SiC/6061 (25 v/o). These composites and each aluminum specimen without fiber prepared by the method in Fig.1, were heat-treated under conditions as shown in Table 1. The tensile strength of these composites as both fabricated and heat-treated were examined with a gauge length of 30 mm and a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min in both the axial and transverse directions. And five composite specimens were tested. The configuration of the tensile test specimen is shown in Fig.2.

Fig.1 The fabrication of SiC/Al by liquid metal pressing method.

Table 1. Matrix properties after heat treatment

Matrix	Condition of Heat Treatment	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)
1100	350°C, 0.3 ks	89	35
5052	350°C, 9.0 ks	193	25
6061	430°C, 7.2 ks	124	25

Fig.2 Composite tensile specimen configuration (dimensions in mm)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows mechanical properties of SiC/1100, SiC/5052 and SiC/6061. The axial tensile strength (0°) of SiC/1100 and SiC/6061, 861(930*)MPa and 690(710*)MPa obeys the R.O.M.(rule of mixtures) strength predictions, respectively. But that of SiC/5052(781 MPa) is deviated from the R.O.M. prediction(1060 MPa). This is caused by the existence of cavities in SiC/5052. These cavities are shown in Fig.3. In the SiC/1100 composite, there are no cavities and 1100-aluminum is permeated among the SiC fiber as shown in Fig.4.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of SiC/Al composites

	SiC/1100		SiC/5052		SiC/6061	
	As-Fab.	H.T.	As-Fab.	H.T.	As-Fab.	H.T.
V_f (%)	35		40		25	
Tensile Strength (MPa)	861 (930*)	836	781 (1060*)	784	690 (710*)	680
(90°)	15		10		140	
Elastic Modulus (E_1) (GPa)	89	92	121	130	100	119
(E_2)	73	81	105	111	77	86

* Value shows R.O.M. prediction.
The above value is the average of five specimens.

Fig.3 Photomicrograph of SiC/5052 ($V_f = 40\%$) 140X

Fig.4 Photomicrograph of SiC/1100 ($V_f = 35\%$) 140X

Some typical stress-strain curves are shown in Fig.5 to compare the mechanical behavior of SiC/1100, SiC/5052 and SiC/6061 as fabricated. The SiC/1100 shows a marked deviation from linear behavior prior to failure at the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of 932 MPa. Its shows an initial primary elastic modulus ($E_1 = 87$ GPa) and a lower secondary elastic modulus ($E_2 = 70$ GPa). The SiC/5052 shows a little deviation from linear behavior. It is $E_1 = 128$ GPa, $E_2 = 101$ GPa and UTS= 805 MPa. The SiC/6061 exhibits a elastic stress-strain relationship. It is $E_1 = 97$ GPa, $E_2 = 78$ GPa and UTS= 690 MPa. The elastic modulus of these composites changes from E_1 to E_2 , and this change is attributed to the onset of microplastic deformation in the matrix (2).

Fig.5(a) Stress-strain behavior of SiC/1100 composite (typical as fabricated)

Fig.5(b) Stress-strain behavior of SiC/5052 composite

Fig.5(c) Stress-strain behavior of SiC/6061 composite

Fig.9 Comparison of stress-strain curves in SiC/1100, as fabricated and heat-treated

The SiC/6061 fractures in a brittle manner, but the SiC/1100 has ductile-like behavior. These behaviors are illustrated from the shape of fracture observed by optical microscope. In Fig.6, the fracture of both fibers and matrix occurs simultaneously in SiC/6061, but the fracture of SiC/1100 exhibits more jagged, and the shape of a saw blade.

Tensile fracture surfaces of SiC/1100 and SiC/6061 by scanning electron microscope are shown in Fig.7 and 8 in both axial and transverse fracture. The fracture surface of SiC/1100 shows the separation of SiC fiber and the matrix and pull-out of SiC fiber. These observations are not made for the fracture surface in SiC/6061. This difference in fracture behavior is also indicated in Fig.8. Tensile fracture surface at the transverse direction shows that the SiC fiber-1100 Al bonding is weak, but the SiC fiber-6061 Al bonding is excellent. The transverse strengths of SiC/1100 and SiC/5052 are less than those of 1100 and 5052 Al, but the transverse strength of SiC/6061 is higher than that of 6061. This high transverse strength in SiC/6061 composite shows also that fiber-6061 bonding in this composite is excellent in comparison with SiC/1100 and SiC/5052.

Fig.6 Tensile fracture mode of SiC/Al composites

The SiC/1100 composite was heat-treated under the condition shown in Table 1. Fig.9 shows the comparison of stress-strain curves between SiC/1100 as fabricated and as heat-treated. Both behaviors are same. The stress-strain behaviors of SiC/5052 and SiC/6061 is similar to that of SiC/1100. And, the pull-out of SiC fiber from matrix was observed in SiC/1100 and SiC/5052 as heat-treated, and therefore the tensile fracture modes of composites as heat-treated were similar to that of composites as fabricated as shown in Fig.6.

In all case, the elongations of composites as heat-treated are smaller than those of composites as fabricated. But, the difference of the elongation is very small. In this study, the heat treatment conditions as shown in Table 1, is commonly annealing treatment. This annealing treatment had no effect on the mechanical properties of SiC/Al composite.

(a) SiC/1100 $100\mu\text{m}$

(b) SiC/6061 $100\mu\text{m}$

(c) SiC/1100 $20\mu\text{m}$

(d) SiC/6061 $20\mu\text{m}$

Fig.7 Tensile fracture surfaces of SiC/Al by SEM

(a) SiC/1100 $20\mu\text{m}$

(b) SiC/6061 $20\mu\text{m}$

Fig.8 Transverse tensile fracture surfaces of SiC/Al

SUMMARY

The mechanical properties of SiC/1100, SiC/5052 and SiC/6061 composites were examined.

- 1) In SiC/5052, 5052-Al was not well permeated among the SiC fibers, but in both SiC/1100 and SiC/6061, Al was well permeated among the SiC fibers and exhibiting excellent compatibility between SiC fiber and 1100 or 6061 Al.
- 2) The fracture behavior of SiC/1100 was ductile-like and that of SiC/6061 was brittle. These are illustrated from SiC fiber-Al bonding. SiC/6061 bonding is excellent in comparison with SiC/1100 bonding. However, the tensile strengths of both composites obey the rule of mixtures predictions.
- 3) The elongations of the composites as annealed are smaller than those of the composites as fabricated.

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